

Condensation of Phenylsulphonylacetic Acid with Aryl Aldehydes

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Manuscript received 21 June 1974; accepted 19 September 1974

Some new α,β -unsaturated sulphones were prepared by the condensation of phenylsulphonylacetic acid with various aryl aldehydes in the presence of catalytic amounts of benzylamine. Their IR spectra have been analysed and it appears that all the compounds are *trans* isomers.

THE condensation of aryl sulphonylacetic acids with aromatic aldehydes in the presence of different reagents resulted with the formation of β -amines and α,β -unsaturated sulphones.^{1,2} Similar condensations³ in the presence of benzylamine gave higher yields of the unsaturated sulphones while reducing the formation of β -amino-sulphones to a negligible amount. For our studies on aryl cyclopropyl sulphones we require a series of α,β -unsaturated sulphones as intermediates. A number of new unsaturated sulphones (Table 1) are synthesized by the condensation of phenylsulphonylacetic acid with aromatic aldehydes in the presence of catalytic amounts of benzylamine. The preparation of unsaturated sulphones has been reported by several routes⁴⁻⁶ but the synthetic utility of this procedure³ appears to be more elegant and convenient under simpler experimental conditions affording good yields of the unsaturated sulphones.

The UV spectra of all these unsaturated sulphones showed a long wavelength band around 270-320 nm, a second band around 220-236 nm, and a third band with high intensity at 200-210 nm region. The IR spectra of most of these sulphones exhibited a band in the region 1680-1620 cm^{-1} (ν C=C) and another band in the region 1000-975 cm^{-1} (δ Ch out-of-plane) characteristic of *trans* ethylenic compounds.⁷⁻⁹ They have also showed bands in the region¹⁰ 1300-1280 cm^{-1} (δ CH in-plane). It may be concluded from the spectral data that all these unsaturated sulphones are *trans* isomers. These compounds have also exhibited very strong peaks characteristic of sulphone groups¹¹⁻¹³ in the regions 1360-1300 and 1160-1120 cm^{-1} . Strong peaks in the

region 1100-1075 cm^{-1} characteristic of S-aryl group frequency,¹⁴ were also displayed by all these compounds. Medium to strong bands appeared in the spectra of all these compounds in the range¹⁵ 1590-1570 cm^{-1} which may be considered as a positive indication of the conjugation of double bonds with the aromatic rings.

Experimental

All melting points were determined on a Mel-Temp apparatus and are uncorrected. The elemental analyses were performed by Dr. R. D. MacDonald, Australian Microanalytical Service. UV absorption measurements were determined in 95% ethanol with a Beckmann model DU-2 Ultraviolet Spectrophotometer and IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer model 700 in nujol mulls.

General Procedure : The condensations were effected by refluxing a mixture of phenylsulphonylacetic acid (0.01 mole), aryl aldehyde (0.01 mole) and benzylamine (0.2 ml) in glacial acetic acid (6 ml) for 90 min. The cooled reaction mixture was treated with dry ether (50 ml) and refrigerated for 12 hr. The product separated was filtered and the ethereal layer was washed successively with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate (15 ml), sodium bisulphite (15 ml), dilute hydrochloric acid (20 ml) and finally with water. Evaporation of the dried ethereal layer yielded normally a solid product. However, in cases where a syrupy substance separated, was solidified on treatment with a small amount of isopropanol. The relevant data on the compounds synthesized are given in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1— $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{SO}_2\text{CH}=\text{CHR}$

Sl. No.	R	Yield %	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Found %		Calcd. %	
					C	H	C	H
1.	4- $\text{CH}_3\text{CONHC}_6\text{H}_4$	50.5 ^a	82-83	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_3\text{S}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	60.55	5.16	60.17	5.37
2.	3- BrC_6H_4	46.4 ^b	103-104	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{BrO}_2\text{S}$	51.89	3.33	52.04	3.43
3.	4- BrC_6H_4	61.9 ^a	154-155	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{BrO}_2\text{S}$	52.16	3.51	52.04	3.43
4.	3-Br-4- $\text{CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3$	58.0 ^a	157-158	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{BrO}_3\text{S}$	51.42	3.75	51.41	3.71
5.	3- ClC_6H_4	59.3 ^b	98.5-99	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClO}_2\text{S}$	60.44	4.09	60.33	3.98
6.	2:3-(CH_3O) ₂ C_6H_3	64.4 ^c	114-115	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4\text{S}$	63.04	5.32	63.13	5.30
7.	2:5-(CH_3O) ₂ C_6H_3	50.0 ^d	135-136	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4\text{S}$	63.17	5.25	63.13	5.30
8.	3:4-(CH_3O) ₂ C_6H_3	45.2 ^a	144-145	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4\text{S}$	63.40	5.35	63.13	5.30
9.	2- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4$	38.9 ^a	91-92	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3\text{S}$	66.44	5.54	66.64	5.59
10.	2- FC_6H_4	45.2 ^a	85-86	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{FO}_2\text{S}$	64.24	4.29	64.12	4.23
11.	4-(CH_3) ₂ CHC_6H_4	35.2 ^a	104-104.5	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{S}$	71.10	6.12	71.29	6.33
12.	2- $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	48.4 ^b	84-84.5	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{S}$	69.50	5.44	69.77	5.46
13.	1-Naphthyl	38.2 ^a	102-103	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{S}$	73.67	4.88	73.45	4.79
14.	1-Pyrene	68.0 ^d	195-196	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{S}$	77.93	4.40	78.25	4.38

Products recrystallized from (a) 95% ethanol, (b) isopropanol, (c) methanol, and (d) glacial acetic acid.

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRA OF $C_6H_5SO_2CH=CHR$

Compd. No.	Band range cm^{-1}						
	$\nu C=C$	δCH (in-plane)	δCH (out-of-plane)	νSO_2	$\nu S-Aryl$	Aromatic ring conjugation with $C=C$	
1.		1280(s)	978(m)	1298(s)	1139(s)	1080(s)	1578(s)
2.	1637(w)	1287(s)	985(m)	1306(s)	1132(s)	1078(s)	1574(w)
3.		1283(m)	978(m)	1308(s)	1155(s)	1085(m)	1578(m)
4.	1658(w)	1280(s)	968(m)	1302(s)	1138(s)	1080(s)	1584(s)
5.	1645(w)	1275(w)	970(m)	1303(m)	1150(s)	1092(m)	1582(m)
6.	1680(w)	1280(m)	1000(m)	1297(s)	1156(s)	1098(m)	1582(m)
7.	1665(w)	1265(s)	975(m)	1295(s)	1135(s)	1077(s)	1568(s)
8.	1648(w)	1276(m)	1002(s)	1354(m)	1118(s)	1062(m)	1582(m)
9.	1675(w)	1280(s)	990(m)	1308(s)	1140(s)	1085(s)	1567(m)
10.	1640(w)	1282(s)	968(m)	1300(s)	1142(s)	1082(s)	1568(w)
11.		1284(m)	974(m)	1306(s)	1145(s)	1082(s)	1570(w)
12.		1270(m)	968(m)	1295(s)	1135(s)	1078(s)	1585(m)
13.		1277(w)	980(m)	1312(s)	1158(s)	1098(m)	1592(w)
14.	1660(w)	1290(s)	982(w)	1304(s)	1139(s)	1076(s)	1578(s)

s = strong, m=medium, and w=weak

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